

ROLE OF CT IN EVALUATION OF HYDRONEPHROSIS

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INTRODUCTION

Hydronephrosis (HN) means “dilated or swollen” upper urinary tract (kidney). The word “hydro” represents “water” and “nephro” represents “kidney”. It is not a true disease, but rather a descriptive term used to identify the amount of renal dilation from another disease or condition that may be present. HN can involve one or both kidneys. Normally urine flows out of the kidney with low pressure. If this flow pattern is disrupted by dilation of the kidney placing increasing pressure on the delicate internal structures of the central urine collecting system, damage can result through loss of function¹.

Hydronephrosis refers to distension and dilation of the renal pelvis and calyces, usually caused by obstruction of the free flow of urine from the kidney. Untreated, it leads to progressive atrophy of the kidney. One or both kidneys may be affected. In cases of hydronephrosis and hydronephrosis, there is distention of both the ureter and the renal pelvis and calices.⁽²⁾

The signs and symptoms of hydronephrosis depend upon whether the obstruction is acute or chronic, partial or complete, unilateral or bilateral. Hydronephrosis that occurs acutely with

sudden onset (as caused by a and ribs). hydronephrosis that develops gradually will generally cause no pain or attacks of a dull discomfort. An obstruction that occurs at the urethra or bladder outlet can cause pain and pressure resulting from distension of the bladder. Blocking the flow of urine will commonly result in urinary tract infections which can lead to the development of additional stones, fever, and blood or pus in the urine. If complete obstruction occurs, kidney failure may follow.⁽³⁾ Mild symptoms of hydronephrosis include urinating more frequently and an increased **urge to urinate**. Other potentially severe symptoms you may experience are pain in the abdomen or flank, nausea, vomiting, pain when urinating, incomplete voiding, or bladder emptying, fever.

Blood tests may show impaired kidney function (elevated urea or creatinine) or electrolyte imbalances such as hyponatremia or hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis. Urinalysis may indicate an elevated pH due to the secondary destruction of nephrons within the affected kidney. Physical examination may detect a palpable abdominal or flank mass caused by the enlarged kidney.

Causes

Hydronephrosis is the result of any of several abnormal pathophysiological occurrences. Structural abnormalities of the junctions between the kidney, ureter, and bladder that lead to hydronephrosis can occur during fetal development. Some of these congenital defects have been identified as inherited conditions; however the benefits of linking genetic testing to early.⁽⁴⁾

Hydronephrosis can also result from the reverse flow of urine from the bladder back into the kidneys. This reflux can be caused by some of the factors listed above as well as compression of the bladder outlet into the urethra by prostatic enlargement or impaction of feces in the colon, as well as abnormal contractions of bladder muscles resulting from neurological dysfunction or other muscular disorders. Diagnostic workup depends on the age of the

patient, as well as whether the hydronephrosis was detected incidentally or prenatally or is associated with other symptoms. (5)

Types : 1. Open hydronephrosis : The hydronephrotic sac still communicates with the lower urinary tract because the obstruction is incomplete.

2 Intermittent hydronephrosis: The obstruction becomes complete intermittently so that at one stage there is oliguria with pain in the loin and enlargement of the hydronephrotic sac, and thereafter (as the obstruction passes off), there is passage of large quantity of urine with diminution in the size of the sac.

3 Closed hydronephrosis: outflow from the hydronephrotic sac ceases as the obstruction becomes complete and there is no communication of the sac with the lower urinary tract.

Compression of one or both ureters can also be caused by other developmental defects not completely occurring during the fetal stage such as an abnormally placed vein, artery, or tumor. Bilateral compression of the ureters can occur during pregnancy due to enlargement of the uterus. Changes in hormone levels during this time may also affect the muscle contractions of the bladder, further complicating this condition. Sources of obstruction that can arise from other various causes include kidney stones, blood clots, or retroperitoneal fibrosis. (Koh JS,et al,1998)⁶.

Imaging studies such as an intravenous urogram (IVU), ultrasound, CT or MRI, are important investigations in determining the presence and/ or cause of hydronephrosis. (Kay& Robert ,1999).whilst ultrasound allows for visualization of the ureters and kidneys (and determine the presence of hydronephrosis and/or hydroureter), an IVU is useful for assessing the anatomical location of the obstruction. Ante grade or retrograde pyelography will show similar findings to an IVU but offer a therapeutic option as well.

The choice of imaging depends on the clinical presentation (history, symptoms and examination findings). In the case of renal colic (one sided loin pain usually accompanied by a trace of blood in the urine) the initial investigation is usually a spiral or helical CT scan. CT has the advantage of showing whether there is any obstruction of flow of urine causing hydronephrosis as well as demonstrating the function of the other kidney. Many stones are not visible on plain x ray or IVU but 99% of stones are visible on CT and therefore CT is becoming a common choice of initial investigation. CT is not used however, when there is a reason to avoid radiation exposure e.g. pregnancy.

In 1974, Dr Robert Steven Ledley gave the whole-body CT scanner. Dr Ledley, Physicist who was credited with inventing the first full body CT scanner, a machine that revolutionized medical diagnostics by allowing doctors to gaze inside their patient's tissues without ever touching a scalpel. Dr Ledley was trained as a dentist. Then in 1973, he introduced one of the most powerful diagnostic aides since the discovery of x-rays in 1895. He called his invention the automatic computerized transverse axial scanner (ACTA). It was in effect, the first machine capable of producing cross-sectional images of any part of the body. When Dr Ledley's machine began to become widely available in the mid 1970s, the journal of the American medical association called it remarkable and fundamentally new technique. Renal ultrasonography and excretory urography traditionally have been the primary means of investigating the kidney, but CT has rapidly gained ground and conventional IV pyelography is now rarely performed (Chen and Zagoria, 1999).⁷

In the present series of 40 consecutive cases, we have tried to demonstrate the efficiency and reliability of CT scan in evaluation of hydronephrosis of Radiologically diagnosed patient attending the department of radio- diagnosis and imaging subharti medical college. The institute has a vast referral catchment area in an around city meerut in western U.P.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

A prospective study was conducted on 40 patients with clinical impression of hydronephrosis from 1st Jan 2017 to 30th May 2018. Patients were subjected to CT scanning and studied in N.S.C.B Subharti Medical College, Meerut. All patients who were referred to Department of Radio-Diagnosis Imaging and Interventional Radiology with clinical signs and symptoms of hydronephrosis were studied. Study was performed with 128 slice CT scanner PHILIPS INGUNITY machine. A minimum of 40 cases were intended to be taken up for study, but the scope of increasing the number of cases also exist depending on the availability within the study period. **Inclusion criteria:** All patients with radiologically diagnosed Hydronephrosis, Cases were included irrespective of age/sex. **Exclusion criteria:** Pregnancy, Uncooperative patients, Patient who did not give consent. Data are collected and performed in excel, after that all data is analyzed by using SPSS 19 version software. For all data frequencies, table graph is plotted and by applying chi-square test with p-value and sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV has been calculated.

RESULTS

The study was conducted from 1st Jan 2017 to 30 May 2018. This study included all the patients who were referred by the clinical departments of CSS hospital, N.S.C.B. Subharti Medical College, Meerut and radiologically diagnosed with hydronephrosis. Detailed history and relevant examination were done and recorded. A total number of 40 cases were evaluated in our study. CT scan was done as requested by the clinical departments.

Patients were evaluated in the form of brief requisition (Annexure I) and then subjected to CT KUB/Abdomen as advised. On these scans, the imaging evaluation in the form of etiological factor for hydronephrosis, its location and characteristics was done.

1. **Age wise distribution** : The maximum patients enrolled in study was belonged to 46 to 50 years of age.

Fig 1: Age wise distribution

2. **Gender Distribution**: All patients included in study were male compare to the female.

Fig 2: Gender Distribution

3. Radiological assessment

a) **Distribution of hydronephrosis depend on anatomical position:** Maximum number of patients was diagnosed with unilateral hydronephrosis.

Table 1: Distribution of hydronephrosis depend on anatomical position

Side of hydronephrosis	Male		Female		Total		P - value
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	
Left	9	39.13	7	41.18	16	40	0.987
Right	11	47.83	8	47.06	19	47.5	
Bilateral	3	13.04	2	11.76	5	12.5	
Total	23	100	17	100	40	100	

b) **Distribution of hydronephrosis in gender:** Maximum patients were diagnosed with mild hydronephrosis (80%).

Table 2: Distribution of hydronephrosis in gender

Gender	Male		Female		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Mild	18	78.26	14	82.35	32	80
Moderate	4	17.39	3	17.65	7	17.5
Severe	1	4.35	0	0	1	2.5
Total	23	100	17	100	40	100

c) **Evaluation of CT imaging investigation of the Patients:** NCCT KUB most common investigation for KUB Imaging in Computed tomography Scanning.

Table 3: Evaluation of CT imaging investigation of the Patients:

INVESTIGATION	NO. OF CASES	%
NCCT KUB (ROUTINE)	22	55
CECT KUB (ROUTINE POSTCONTRAST)	2	5
CECT ABDOMEN (ROUTINE POST CONTRAST)	16	49
TOTAL	40	100

DISCUSSION

The prospective study was done to check the efficiency and reliability of computed tomography in evaluation hydronephrosis and to assess the severity of hydronephrosis. Most of the studies have been done in general population without any discrimination. In the present study of 40 patients, we found that male 23 (57.5%) and female 17(42.5%) in number male: female ratio of 1:1.35. **Fowler CG, et al in (2004):**⁸ study about the male female ratio of hydronephrosis and concluded that it is 2:1. **Joshi KS et al in 2014**⁹ concluded that 47.2% were female and 52.9% were male. In our study, patients were above 1 year included and the youngest patients was 13 years old boy and eldest was 70 years old male and female. The maximum number of patients in our study belonged to 46-60 years (40%), 31-45 years (32.5%) and more than 60 year (10%). Regarding the age group the study found that the most common age group was 46-60 years with female predominance. Maximum number of patients was in the age group of 46-60 years (40%), Male 29 (39.13%) and Female 21 (41.17%).

Concerning the gender, the study found that the high percentage of hydronephrosis in male (57.5%) more than female (42.5). **Song Y1 et al in (2015)**¹⁰ mild- 70.6 %, moderate- 27.8% and severe- 1.5%. Mean patient age was 47 years.

In our study severity of the hydronephrosis was mild- 80%, moderate 17.5% and severe- 2.5% mean patient age was 45.35 years. **Fowler CG, et al in (2004)**⁸ right side is most

commonly affected. In our study right side is affected in 19 (47.5%) patients, left side in 16 (40%) patients and bilateral hydronephrosis was diagnosed in 5(12.5) patients.

CONCLUSION

Our study found that mild hydronephrosis was present in 80% of cases, moderate in 17.5%, and severe in 2.5%. Mild hydronephrosis was the most common, affecting 32 patients (80%), with the right side more frequently involved (19 patients, 47.5%) compared to the left (16 patients, 40%). Five patients (12.5%) had severe hydronephrosis. We demonstrated that CT scans with appropriate imaging parameters improve sensitivity and specificity in assessing hydronephrosis, making them valuable for enhancing diagnostic accuracy. However, due to the small sample size, further research is needed to confirm these findings.

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